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UNIVERSITY OF NORTHWEST

**A GENERAL COMPARISON OF THE DIFFERENCES AND THE COMMON
CHARACTERISTICS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL APPROACHES TO
MEDICAL PSYCHOLOGY**

LICENSE THESIS

Mete ÖZKÖK

Thesis Advisor: Dr. Bilal Semih BOZDEMİR

2007

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TERM PROJECT APPROVAL

The study titled “GENERAL COMPARISON OF THE DIFFERENCES AND THE COMMON CHARACTERISTICS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL APPROACHES TO MEDICAL PSYCHOLOGY” Regulation prepared by Mete ÖZKÖK was published on 2007, in accordance with the relevant articles of the “University of Northwest, an Exam graduation project in the Psychological Science Undergraduate Program”. evaluated and accepted.

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SUMMARY

A GENERAL COMPARISON OF THE DIFFERENCES AND THE COMMON CHARACTERISTICS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL APPROACHES TO MEDICAL PSYCHOLOGY

Mete ÖZKÖK

Department of Psychology

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"Biomedical expertise is required to provide proper medical care, but this is insufficient on its own." In order to understand the nature of dysfunctions and how to communicate with patients and doctors, psychosocial knowledge is required. "In the medical area, we cannot allow the careless and stupid" (Lean Eisenberg, 2000). This sentence was extracted verbatim from an editorial address that was presented in the British Journal of Psychiatry to mark the journal's entry into the twenty-first century. Eisenberg is recognized by many as one of the most important figures in psychiatry. Like many other eminent figures in the profession at the turn of the century, L. Eisenberg, a prominent figure in medicine, had to deal with the realities of integration. His analysis makes it evident how crucial it is to combine the biological, behavioral, and psychological sciences in order to understand how the mind and brain function and interact to generate normalcy or abnormality. Clinical health psychology is predicted to be a key component of this integrated approach. Unfortunately, a lot of individuals who work in the medical field don't fully comprehend this situation. Recent developments in medical, psychological, and physiological research have directly led to the emergence of a new way of thinking about health and illness. The biopsychosocial paradigm, which attributes health and illness to a confluence of biological qualities (such as genetic predisposition), behavioral traits (such as way of life, stress, and health attitudes), and social environments, reflects this. According to the biopsychosocial paradigm, a variety of variables, including genetic predisposition, impact both health and sickness (eg, cultural influences, family

relationships, and social support). This perspective on health and illness has several benefits, both practically and scientifically. Those who seek treatment from an interdisciplinary team that includes mental health professionals are at a decreased risk of serious medical issues, and their care is more successful and less expensive. The main advantage of receiving therapy from an interdisciplinary group of behavioral health professionals is this.

Keywords: *Medical Psychology, Medical Psychology, Comparison of Medical and Medical Psychology, Differences between Medical and Medical Psychology,*

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DECLARATION OF COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL PRINCIPLES AND RULES

I declare that I have acted in accordance with scientific ethical principles and rules in the preparation of this term project, that I have referred to the sources used within the scope of the study in accordance with scientific norms and that I have included them in the bibliography . I declare that I accept all moral and legal consequences that will arise in the event of a situation contrary to this statement I made regarding my work.

Mete ÖZKÖK

Introduction

The biomedical paradigm, where the primary attention of the scientist and practitioner is on the biological components of the issue, has recently been the focus of dealing with health and illness. It's important to highlight that this paradigm has lately been questioned. It was widely thought that good health was defined as the absence of sickness or damage and that the existence of these circumstances was a sign of bad health. The degree of biological injury might be lessened since the model needed biological interventions to obtain effective therapy. As a direct consequence, medical practitioners were split into two categories:

1. *Doctors who adhere to the biomedical school of thought and have full authority to treat patients;*
2. *And his assistants, whose responsibility is to carry out the instructions of the doctors.*

The medical system and medical practice have undergone substantial changes as a consequence of the growing understanding of the relationship between the body and mind. What sets apart the current holistic healthcare approach is this transition away from the biological paradigm and toward biopsychosocial medicine. The biopsychosocial model reflects the basic notion that biological, psychological, and social factors interact in an interdependent or systemic manner to preserve health or induce illness. The paradigm is based on this viewpoint.

Biopsychosocial Paradigm

This approach, sometimes referred to as the biopsychosocial paradigm, has gained widespread acceptance and has been used by the World Health Organization (WHO). The study of behavioral health is quickly elevating to the position of being the most significant area of the biopsychosocial science since behavior plays such a significant impact in both mental and physical health. The way we perceive events affects how we act in response to them in terms of adopting constructive or destructive habits and changing our behavioral patterns. Cassidy explained how behavior may impact the body in a beneficial or negative manner by stating that lifestyles, life events, and poor habits are closely tied to health and illness. Personality may predispose a person's body to a wide range of dysfunctions, and our health-related attitudes affect whether we hear or pay heed to the advice given by medical specialists.

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Psychology, the study of behavior and mental processes, emphasizes knowledge and comprehension of these many components heavily (for example, lifelong development, learning, motivations, experiences, emotions, cognition, social behavior and attitudes, personality, etc.). It also aims to comprehend the roles played by biological, behavioral, and social factors in health and sickness. Thus, psychologists are key players in the process of discovering how biological, behavioral, and social factors affect health and sickness as providers of behavioral health. They possess the information, skills, and training required to comprehend how fundamental cognitive and behavioral processes (such as cognition, emotion, motivation, development, personality, social interaction, and culture) predispose to the emergence of systemic dysfunctions in the body. Students learn how these cognitive and behavioral processes are influenced, what changes them, and how these dysfunctions are recognized and addressed. On the other hand, they have received training on how to recognize and understand these dysfunctions. Moreover, they are skilled and qualified to carry out a range of psychological, psychodiagnostics, and psychotherapeutic treatments that enhance and have an impact on their capacity to function in a range of situations and roles while overcoming such difficulties. Also, they assist people in making lifestyle and behavioral changes to both prevent and treat health issues. The need for psychologists to work in hospitals and other healthcare facilities has increased as a direct consequence of this, and clinical health psychology has become one of the most significant professions in healthcare.

The Growth of Psychology as Both a Health Specialty and a Subject of Study

Many subspecialties and specialties within psychology have emerged as a consequence of the discipline's expansion as a research and health specialty. Some of the subfields that fall within the purview of this discipline include clinical psychology, health psychology (sometimes referred to as medical psychology or behavioral medicine), clinical neuropsychology, counseling psychology, rehabilitation psychology, community psychology, and pediatric psychology. In a Therapeutic Setting, Psychology Clinical psychology focuses on the use of psychological knowledge and abilities, as well as research and intervention techniques in connection to health and sickness, especially mental health.

According to the American Psychological Association, clinical psychology is "a clinical field that involves the provision of diagnosis, assessment, treatment plan, therapy, preventive, and counseling services to patients in emergency departments, inpatient units, and hospital clinics.

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The Canadian Psychological Association offers another definition, describing it as a broad area of practice and study within the discipline of psychology that applies psychological principles to the evaluation, prevention, recovery, and rehabilitation of psychological distress, disability, and dysfunctional behavior as well as the promotion of health risk behaviors and psychological and physical well-being.

In general, clinical psychology is an interdisciplinary area that integrates theory, research, and practice to assist human adjustment, adjustment, and personal development as well as to explain, predict, and treat maladjustment, disorders, and disorders.

As a result, it places a strong emphasis on the cognitive, affective, biological, psychological, social, and behavioral aspects of how people behave and interact in a variety of cultural situations and at all socioeconomic levels.

A Series of Sub-specializations

The field of clinical psychology encompasses a variety of subspecialties. Clinical forensic psychology, clinical gero-psychology, clinical psychology of learning impairments, clinical psychology of drug misuse, and clinical psychology of children and adolescents are a few of these subspecialties. Mental health/medical psychology Health psychology, health promotion and maintenance, illness prevention and treatment, etiology and health, diagnostic correlates of disease and associated dysfunction, and advancement of the healthcare system and health policy are all connected to good health. Medical psychology or behavioral medicine are other names for health psychology.

In the fields of disease prevention and management, health promotion and maintenance, identifying psychological variables that contribute to physical sickness, development of the health care system, and health formulation, health psychologists use psychological research and methodologies.

The following is a list of the objectives of health psychology:

“examination of psychological, social, emotional and behavioral factors in physical and mental illness; improvement of the health system and formulation of health policy; and understanding the etiology of disease, promotion and maintenance of health, prevention, diagnosis, treatment

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and rehabilitation of physical and mental illnesses; The study of psychological, social, emotional and behavioral factors in physical and mental illness”

Health psychologists are thus interested in researching how biological, psychological, and social factors influence health and illness. As a consequence, they participate in activities including illness prevention and treatment, maintaining and promoting healthy habits, and researching and enhancing the healthcare system.

Clinically Focused Neuropsychology

Clinical neuropsychology is the study of the relationship between the brain and behavior, particularly how abnormalities in brain function might affect behavior and behavioral disorders. A clinical neuropsychologist is a member of the mental health community who focuses on the identification, assessment, and care of patients with brain diseases. Clinical neuropsychologists are often employed by hospitals and other healthcare facilities in the clinical psychology, neuroscience, or neurosurgery departments.

Counseling and Psychological Services

Counseling psychology is a branch of psychology that focuses on assisting individuals and groups in improving their well-being, reducing their discomfort, handling crises, finding solutions to issues, and sharpening their decision-making skills. Psychologists that specialize in this area of psychology assist clients in enhancing all these facets of their life. The great majority of persons who seek counseling do so because they are experiencing minor psychological issues. On the other hand, counseling psychologists deal with clients of all ages, including children, adolescents, adults, and the elderly. In addition to hospitals and medical facilities, academic institutions, jails, schools, enterprises and industries, community health centers, and more, they may be found in a broad range of organizations. Counseling psychologists then assist clients in adjusting to change or making the required lifestyle changes. They aid individuals and organizations in dealing with issues pertaining to their own well-being, other people's relationships, their jobs, their hobbies, their health, and managing crises. While they may have the choice to work independently, they could decide to work as an academic counselor, clinical psychologist, child psychologist, or health psychologist.

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Psychology of Rehabilitation Initiatives

The study of and care for people with chronic and incapacitating medical disorders is the subject of the applied clinical specialty in professional psychology known as rehabilitation psychology. Rehabilitation psychologists treat patients recuperating from accidents and strokes as well as those with mental retardation and developmental abnormalities brought on by conditions including cerebral palsy, epilepsy, and autism. They help persons who have a hard time adapting to their surroundings and often work with other medical specialists. They address issues including pain management, growth personally, and relationships with others at work and at home. They now take part in more public health efforts aimed at preventing disability. Also, they provide expert testimony in court cases about the causes, consequences, and rehabilitation required to enhance a person's quality of life. Children's Psychology The study of children, adolescents, and their families' physical and mental growth, health, and sickness falls under the umbrella of the multidisciplinary area of pediatric psychology.

Pediatric psychologists are thus in charge of diagnosing, assessing, and treating psychological issues that have an impact on children's and adolescents' physical health or are a direct outcome of a dysfunction in that health. They also work to improve mental health services, advance development and health, and protect kids and teenagers from damage and sickness.

The Biological Paradigm Not Meeting Optimal Health Requirements

Sadly, the biological paradigm, which is unable to provide for optimum health requirements, continues to confine medical education and training in the overwhelming majority of poor nations. The intellectual challenge, according to Lisenberg, is in the pharmacy because "neither mindless nor brainless can be accepted in medicine," alluding to the fact that "neither mindless nor brainless can be tolerated in conduct in its social context." A biopsychosocial strategy must be used in order to provide a full solution.

Psychologists' main role in the medical treatment of sickness up to the mid-1960s was to evaluate the psychopathology of the patients. As a direct consequence of increased understanding of the significance and persistence of behavioral and psychosocial elements in the genesis of dysfunctions, psychologists have increased their degree of skill in diagnosing and treating the behavioral components of disease. As a consequence, psychologists are now more often referred to as health care practitioners than as providers of mental health care. delivery of healthcare as

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academics, therapists, researchers, and administrators. The focus of this study, however, is only on the administrative duties that psychologists carry out in medical settings; it does not include the roles that psychologists have in fostering health and preventing sickness. Psychologists must complete significant training, have a high level of education, and conduct themselves with professionalism when it comes to ethical standards and codes of behavior in order to operate in the health sector. When a teen enrolls in college, they often start a new chapter in their lives. Students face additional obstacles during this transitional phase. Making autonomous choices about their lives and careers, adjusting to the academic rigors of an unstructured learning environment, and engaging in conversation with a broad range of unfamiliar individuals are a few of these hurdles. Many kids are also often requested to move further away from their support systems and leave their family for the first time (Cleary et al., 2011). As a consequence of these issues, college students may see a decline in their mental health and overall wellbeing. In reality, there is evidence that students' mental health is under strain from the time they begin their studies at a university and that this pressure diminishes during their education but does not go back to where it was before they entered college (Macaskill, 2013; Mey & Yin, 2015). (Cooke et al., 2006; Bewick et al., 2010). Also, the probability of having typical psychological issues including stress, worry, and depression rises during adolescence and peaks around age 25. (Kessler et al., 2007). As a result, college students are a group that is especially susceptible to the impacts of these diseases.

Method

During the last several decades, there has been a sharp increase in the proportion of college students who are worried about their physical and mental health. Three connected problems are probably at blame for this. First of all, current study indicates a rise in the severity of mental disorders and help-seeking, despite the fact that college students claim their mental health levels are equal to their non-university counterparts (Blanco et al., 2008). For university students in underdeveloped nations in particular, this is true (Wong et al., 2006; Hunt and Eisenberg, 2010; Verger et al., 2010; Auerbach et al., 2018; Lipson et al., 2019). Some experts have described these trends as an imminent "mental health calamity" in higher education institutions (Kadison and DiGeronimo, 2004; Evans et al., 2018).

Second, psychological discomfort in early adulthood is linked to both short- and long-term unfavorable consequences, such as low college attendance, performance, and completion (King et

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al., 2006; Antaramian, 2015). Long-term effects include broken relationships, persistent mental health issues, college dropout, reduced employment rates, and decreased personal income (Kerr & Capaldi, 2011). (Fergusson et al., 2007). Finally, there is widespread agreement that post-secondary educational institutions provide a single integrated environment that includes academic, professional, and social activities in addition to health care and other support services. This presents a special chance to enhance young people' mental health and wellbeing, a subject that has lately drawn a lot of attention (Eisenberg et al., 2009; Hunt and Eisenberg, 2010). There is increasing worry that the resources offered to help students are not developing at a similar rate as colleges continue to expand (Blanco et al., 2008; Eisenberg et al., 2011; Lipson et al., 2019). Yet, according to many studies (Blanco et al., 2008; Eisenberg et al., 2011; Lipson et al.), the majority of college students with mental health issues and poor wellbeing do not obtain therapy (Davy et al., 2012). Many efforts have been undertaken to clarify the theoretical underpinnings and organizational framework of the discipline using conventional content analysis of the literature in response to the expanding body of research on health and wellbeing. Sharp & Theiler, 2018, Hunt & Eisenberg, 2010, and others. By providing a summary of 200 years of research in this area, this study uses a bibliometric approach to further our understanding of university students' mental health. It provides a rigorous and objective way to find patterns and patterns. r (Van Raan, 2014), which may highlight the scientific foundations of the topic, spot developing theme areas, and pinpoint knowledge gaps (Skute et al., 2019), thereby advancing the field.

Techniques taken from biology and behavioral sciences

Methods from the social sciences, which examine how one's social and cultural context affects mental health and sickness, complement those from the biology and behavioral sciences (Horwitz, 2010). Sociologists are particularly interested in how social factors (such the availability of assistance) affect levels of mental illness and well-being as well as how social structures impact perceptions of and reactions to mental health issues. Compton and Shim (2015) provide an overview of the social determinants of mental health. Similar to that, medical anthropologists concentrate on the mental health ideologies and practices that make up the cultural repertoire both within and across communities (Foster, 1975). Researchers from the domains of business and economics, family and ethnic studies, and educational studies, in addition to the anthropological sciences, have all significantly contributed to the growth of mental health research in a number of ways.

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The Role of the Environment in Sustaining Mental Health

Undoubtedly inherited from widespread psychiatric and psychological traditions developed in Western nations are many of the conceptions of mental health and sickness that are given in published research (Gopalkrishnan, 2018). Yet, cultural norms and traditions undoubtedly affect how other cultures see problems connected to mental health and mental illness. 2012 (Vaillant). Culture affects how people show their symptoms, express those symptoms, deal with psychological difficulties, and decide whether or not to seek therapy, claim Eshun and Gurung (2009). According to this statement, "culture affects how people display symptoms, convey their problems, and manage psychological issues." Fernando (2019) claims that issues with the "mind" originated in non-Western and low- and middle-income nations, where they are often seen today in quite different ways (LMICs). For instance, several cultures provide interpretations on how specific emotions and behaviors are expressed by citing a range of causes, including biological, psychological, social, religious, spiritual, paranormal, and cosmic factors. Asymmetries in knowledge exchange and the invasion of dominant Western narratives into low- and middle-income countries—also known as "medical imperialism"—have resulted from the rejection of alternative non-Western approaches to mental health and mental illness (Timimi, 2010; Summerfield, 2013). To solve this problem, academics have argued that there should be more tolerance for pluralistic conceptualizations of mental disease and wellness. Individuals may use this to examine how knowledge and techniques created in low-income nations can aid people living in high-income countries, as well as to interact with particular types of support they believe are relevant for them (also known as knowledge. "counterflow") (see White et al., 2014). (see White et al., 2014).

The Importance of Emphasizing Good Mental Health and Understanding

How Well-Being is Achieved

Current definitions of mental health include two characteristics, despite the fact that there are many distinct mental health methods that draw from many fields and situations. First, a biopsychosocial viewpoint is used to examine mental health, which considers the impact of biological, psychological, and social components. Second, being mentally well encompasses more than simply being free from mental disease (eg, Bhugra et al., 2013; Galderisi et al., 2015). For instance, the World Health Organization (WHO) describes mental health as "a state in which each person

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fulfills his or her own potential, is able to deal with everyday stressors, can work well, and contributes to their society." [Reference required] a condition of health where one can deal with everyday challenges, work well, and produce fruit (World Health Organization, 2004). (2015) (Galderisi et al.) With the assistance of proponents of positive medicine and psychology, who are among the mental health models with a medical and psychopathological emphasis, research on positive mental health is relatively young, but has expanded quickly in the recent several decades. They pushed for a paradigm change. focusing on diseases and illnesses, shifting to more power-based strategies, and giving greater emphasis to the good aspects of people and other living things. While positive mental health research is still young, it has expanded significantly over the last several decades (Kobau et al., 2011). In order to account for the good aspects of mental health that go beyond the absence of illnesses that affect mental health, the idea of mental health has increasingly become a component of mental health work. While there is no universally accepted definition of the word, subjective well-being (also known as SBW) and psychological well-being have historically been the most contentious approaches to well-being in academic circles. "Health" (PWB) (Diener, 2012). According to popular belief, subjective well-being (SBW), which is closely related to the idea of happiness, is the state of having a high level of good emotions, a low level of negative emotions, and a high level of life satisfaction. (2008) (Deci & Ryan, 2004) PWB's intellectual underpinnings are based on Aristotelian ideas of eudaimonia, or self-actualization. According to Aristotle, achieving one's full potential is the goal of life (Ryff & Singer, 2008) PWB, which has been broadly defined as a state of positive psychological functioning, includes six dimensions: life purpose (i.e., how much participants feel their lives have meaning, purpose, and direction); autonomy (i.e., whether they believe they are living according to their own beliefs); personal growth (i.e., how much they use their unique talents and potential); environmental mastery (i.e., how they use their environment); and how well they manage (Ryff, 1989).

Combining Mental Health, Mental Illness and Well-Being

Positive mental health frameworks have a significant impact on the profession's overall progress, which cannot be understated. Positive emotions and productive functioning being overemphasized in definitions of mental health as essential markers of mental health have lately come under scrutiny because of their tendency to stigmatize certain people and groups. For instance, some individuals may not be able to work or operate well in their workplace owing to personal or environmental limitations (Galderisi et al., 2015). Keyes successfully incorporated the ideas of

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mental disease, mental health, and well-being, as well as other related ideas from ongoing academic study, into a conceptual framework to address these issues. This conceptualization offers a more thorough comprehension of mental health (Keyes, 2005, 2007; Keyes & Michalec, 2010). The paradigm contends that neither pathogenic or salutogenic methods, which emphasize the negative (such as mental disease) or the positive (such as well-being), can adequately characterize a person's mental health on their own. Instead, the model suggests that for a precise description, it is necessary to combine both methods (Keyes & Michalec, 2010). Instead, the paradigm considers that mental disease and well-being are two related but distinct latent continuities when attempting to describe mental health. More specifically, it is possible to think of mental disease and wellbeing as residing on two separate spectrums:

“The first spectrum ranges from the absence to the presence of mental illness, while the second spectrum ranges from low to high. high levels of well-being (Slade, 2010).”

Hence, a high degree of well-being is not necessarily implied by the absence of mental disease. The existence of a mental disease is not necessarily indicated by having a low feeling of wellbeing. Also, in accordance with this paradigm, mental health isn't only defined as a state of high wellbeing; rather, it also includes both the presence and absence of mental disease. Whole mental health, often known as development, is the result of low rates of mental disease and high levels of wellbeing. Instead, "poor mental health" (sometimes referred to as "weakening") describes a state in which there are no outward indications of a mental problem but a low degree of wellbeing is noted. Two further criteria may be argued within the framework of this arrangement. The hallmark of incomplete mental disease, sometimes referred to as "struggle," is a high degree of wellbeing in spite of the existence of a sizable number of mental illness symptoms. Last but not least, severe mental disease symptoms and poor wellbeing are caused by a full state of mental illness, commonly referred to as "confusion" (Keyes & Lopez, 2002).

Current Research

The goal of this study is to explore the area of global science and research on mental health and university students from 1975 to 2020. This is due to the complexity of concepts related to mental health and wellbeing, as well as the many theoretical, disciplinary, and contextual approaches to conceptualizing these concepts. The purpose of this study is to provide fresh insight on the development and status of mental health research on college students. In order to do this, the

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literature written over the last 45 years on university students' mental health and well-being will be mapped and visually presented in terms of their development trajectory, production, and social, intellectual, and conceptual structure. area. At the beginning, the study looks at trends (i.e., growth trajectory) in publication and citation data between 1975 and 2020 to analyze the development of research on mental health and well-being among college students. The report also highlights important periodicals and subject areas that have significantly influenced the development of the profession. It also recognizes important researchers and nations that are driving the creation and distribution of studies on students' productivity and mental health. Lastly, the study analyzes the many scientific partnership networks that exist between various authors and countries (i.e. social structure) The intellectual structure—also known as the fourth step—of research on mental health and well-being in university settings is supported by the emergence of scientific areas. Finally, the study illuminates the conceptual framework or topic foci of 45 years of research on university students' mental health and wellbeing.

Results

Components and Procedures

The literature on mental health and well-being among university students during the last 45 years was mapped using a bibliometric method in this study. The Science Citation Index-Expanded (also known as SCI-Expanded), Social Sciences Citation Index (commonly known as SSCI), Arts & Humanities Citation Index (also known as A&HCI), and Emerging Resources Citation Index are the four directories used to compile the information (ESCI). The WoS database was selected for this study's needs for a variety of acceptable reasons. To begin with, WoS is the most widely utilized resource for bibliometric study and is still regarded as the gold standard (Meho and Yang, 2007). Second, WoS is a database of publications on mental health and wellbeing that have been published in more than 20,000 journals and come from a variety of disciplines and areas of study. As a result, WoS is a resource that spans several disciplines (McVeigh, 2009). Using specialized databases like PubMed brings biases to the search process, and these biases promote a number of scientific disciplines of study. Interdisciplinary databases like WoS and Scopus, however, discriminate against works published in languages other than English and works in the Social Sciences and Humanities (Mongeon and Paul-Hus, 2016). Because of this, WoS's depiction is still not totally accurate. Thirdly, WoS includes publication and citation data going back to 1900, however other databases could provide a broader range of information.

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For instance, Scopus only has complete citation data up to 1996. (Li et al., 2010). Moreover, Google Scholar gives results that include citations that are of varying degrees of accuracy, but PubMed does not offer citation analyses (Falagas et al., 2008). Fourth, research has demonstrated that the WoS journal categorization approach is more accurate than the Scopus database (Wang & Waltman, 2016).

Figure 1 depicts the conceptual paradigm of the technique. Method of Research creating a comprehensive corpus of literature on university students' wellbeing and mental health. three parallel searches are conducted. The several methodologies and viewpoints that have been used in this subject were considered throughout these searches, as described in the section titled "Conceptualizing Mental Health, Mental Illness, and Well-Being: An Overview." These queries' results have been gathered into one database. The last week of January 2020 will be dedicated to all conducted investigations. The first screening was conducted to gather data on research related to mental health in general.

There was only one keyword in the subject area: "sanity."

In the second search, information about disruptive methods to mental health were gathered. The following keywords have been added to the title box for this search:

["mental illness", "mental illness", "mental distress", "psychological distress", "psychopathology", "depression", "anxiety", "stress", "suicide", "eating disorder" and "substance use")."]

Key phrases used in the literature to represent the negative elements of mental health were also incorporated in this search, in addition to the most prevalent mental health issues faced by university students. The third search included words and phrases that described methods that were good for mental health. These terms featured ideas connected to good mental health from several angles (i.e. well-being). While adding, some important phrases were added to the header area. These are as follows:

["health", "health", "health", "life satisfaction", "happiness", "positive emotion", "purpose in life", "personal growth" and "self-determination."]

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To create a search that was exclusively pertinent to students enrolled in higher education, a different set of keywords was added to the title box of each of the three searches. The phrases "university," "college," "higher education," "post-secondary education," "post-secondary education," "undergraduate student," "graduate student," "graduate student," "Ph.D. student," and "Ph.D. student" were also included. The OR Boolean operator was used in each of the three searches to improve the number of results for the query. Apart from that, asterisks were employed as wildcards so that we could define several variations in different words (for example, irregularity and irregularities).

Literature Reviews

Today's population of the globe is significantly impacted by mental health illnesses. Yet because our own brains are the source of all these issues, the discipline of study known as neurology was developed (Kessler et al., 2009). What parts of the brain are accountable for certain behaviors and how can we attempt to modify them? These are questions that the study of neuroscience has answered. It aids in our understanding of the alterations in brain chemistry brought on by different psychotic and neurotic illnesses (Kessler et al., 2009). Stein et al. (2015) looked examined how well neuroscience has been used to the treatment of mental health issues in persons of different ages and ethnic backgrounds. Inappropriate neural connections may cause negative thoughts, actions, and emotions. If psychologists have a thorough grasp of the neurobiology underpinning psychological events, they may better manage the difficulties of their clients and provide more in-depth therapies. They can pinpoint, for instance, which areas of the cortex become active in response to mood disorders or what transpires in the brain when we are subjected to traumatic situations. The goal of neuroscience is to provide mental health therapy a more focused and scientifically supported approach. For instance, individuals with schizophrenia may have cognitive difficulties that make it difficult for them to resume their regular lives or take part in activities that are part of everyday living. This was made clear to medical professionals by research in neuroscience, and as a result, cognitive therapy is now a crucial part of the treatment for schizophrenia, improving the prognosis for patients (Barch, 2005). The use of neuroscience to mental health treatment has produced a number of beneficial results. The study of the underlying causes of many disorders has become easier for therapists and other medical professionals thanks to the discipline of neuroscience. It helps the individual's mental health, happiness, and overall quality of life to improve. Early diagnosis results in a better prognosis, which is made possible by

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the discipline of neurology. It helps to provide a more realistic account of the relationship between the mind and body. Studies on happiness and mental health have developed as a result of neuroscientific research. In their 2013 study, Portugal et al. looked at the neurology of exercise and how it affects mental health.

They came to the conclusion that having a healthy lifestyle has a big impact on our cognitive ability. The relationship between routine exercise and mood changes associated with a range of mental health problems, such as dementia and major depressive disorder, was the topic of research. While athletes made up the bulk of the study's subjects, a broader spectrum of individuals may still benefit from its results. The study's findings supported the notion that regular exercise routines help people get stronger physically and mentally. It boosts a person's confidence, assists him in maintaining emotional control, and guarantees that his body functions as optimally as possible (Portugal et al., 2013). According to the authors, frequent exercise may be one of the things that helps sportsmen be healthier in their personal life, both physically and mentally.

Using Positive Psychology in the Context of Mental Health Counseling

The idea of happiness as a therapeutic aim is one of the most significant contributions that positive psychology makes to the area of counseling and treatment for mental health (Gruman et al., 2017). The Psychological Well-Being Measure and the Happiness Scale, both of which may objectively gauge a person's degree of life satisfaction, were created by researchers in positive psychology. The development of these psychological health techniques gave mental health specialists a strong justification for turning away from issues and toward solutions. The development of people's already-present good habits and attributes started to get greater attention in the area of positive psychology. Positive psychology interventions aim to make clients happier and assist them in finding purpose in their life. Positive psychology-based therapies are recognized to have more enduring effects than traditional psychotherapies and to typically make patients happier. A research on the effectiveness of positive psychotherapy in the treatment of severe depression discovered that when patients got positive therapy, they responded more quickly and shown signs of recovery (Seligman et al., 2006). Researchers also concurred that using techniques to boost optimistic feelings and enhance motivation results in a better prognosis than either medicine alone or conventional psychotherapy (Seligman et al., 2006).

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Every intervention in mental health counseling should aim to bring about this transition, and the discipline of positive psychology provides the motivation to do so. The person should turn his or her focus from the unpleasant symptoms to the happier aspects of his or her life. Positive psychology interventions used in mental health counseling A significant research team has shown the effectiveness of using positive psychology-based therapies in psychotherapy and counseling. In addition to making us happier and more self-assured, it also assists us in regaining the mental equilibrium required to lead a healthy life (Hefferon & Boniwell, 2011).

More diversity, multiculturalism, and humanism has been achieved in the treatment of mental illness because of the introduction of positive psychology therapies and enhanced awareness in counseling (Magyar-Moe et al., 2015). Treatments for mental health disorders are increasingly using interventions based on positive psychology. These may come in the form of individual treatment, counseling at school, or meetings with a life coach. The following are some of the PPIs that psychologists utilize most often today:

treatment that emphasizes patients' strengths This process includes elements of positivism, social psychology, preventative measures, methodological methods that focus on solutions, and individual growth (Rashid, 2015; Smith, 2006). The foundation of strengths-based treatments is the belief that wellbeing and wellbeing are critical aspects that must be addressed, whether there is mental disease. Techniques that emphasize an individual's strengths enable such talents to be recognized and actively used (Jones-Smith, 2011). Techniques with a solution-focus include those that include group sessions, objective evaluations, and dialogue-based therapies. Together, the client and the therapist come up with coping mechanisms for bad situations in order to reach good outcomes (De Jong & Berg, 2002).

The quality-of-life index is based on psychological theory and practice, as well as cognitive and positive treatment (Frisch, 2006). It motivates customers to go after their life objectives, explore their inner selves for a greater feeling of personal satisfaction, and follow their dreams. It also aids individuals in identifying their life objectives. With a focus on quality of life, measurements like the Quality-of-Life Inventory (QOLI) and the CASIO self-satisfaction model may be utilized in treatment. It is founded on the idea of hope, which holds that feelings may be assessed or altered in response to the accomplishment of good objectives (Lopez et al., 2000; Snyder, 2002). People who are having problems in their life expect that treatment would be helpful. To be effective, hope

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therapy tries to raise one's consciousness and assist in re-establishing their sense of self. It follows the following four processes and employs a framework that blends semi-structured, objective, and subjective assessments: looking for hope. A critical first step is to establish a connection with it. As a result, individuals who got a hope-based assistive intervention during therapy sessions scored better on self-esteem and confidence tests, had more defined objectives, and had the motivation to pursue them. the efficiency of hope treatment techniques (Feldman & Kubota, 2015).

The psychological well-being paradigm that Ryff and Singer (1998) created for health and wellness counseling is where the well-being therapy model got its start. Their strategy was adaptable and considered a variety of factors, including environmental proficiency, individual pleasure, a greater sense of purpose in life, acceptance, resilience, and positive social connections (Eren & Kılıc, 2017). Subsequently, well-being treatment was developed by famous psychologist and therapist Giovanni Fava as a powerful positive psychology strategy (Ruini & Fava, 2004). Wellness therapy may improve happiness by assisting clients in identifying and removing mental obstacles. To effectively treat or prevent relapse, wellbeing therapy employs techniques like the ones listed below (Fava, 1999):

“Diary is the practice of writing down important life events and emotions associated with such experiences.”

Important milestones in treatment include confronting worthless beliefs with the help of a therapist and creating workable solutions to dispel them. It is important to promote positive actions like writing, self-expression, active communication, and leading a generally healthy lifestyle.

Positive psychology has developed as a distinct field of psychology after considerable discussion and disagreement over how well it may coexist with clinical or health psychology. We are aware that the goal of clinical psychology is to treat mental health issues while also using the ideas and data gathered previously. The goal of positive psychology is to increase happiness and well-being regardless of whether there is an underlying mental health condition (Steffen et al., 2015). By concentrating on symptom alleviation and a return to a prior level of normality, a mental health illness may only be partly healed, according to study by Csikszentmihalyi and Seligman from 2000. Instead, then concentrating on finding solutions to people's problems, positive psychology aims to help individuals build a feeling of wellbeing and pleasure inside themselves. The goal of positive psychology is to increase people's capacity for resilience in the face of adversity by

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examining the elements that lead to happiness. Contrarily, clinical psychology seeks to aid patients' recovery by concentrating on the causes of sickness. Positive psychology prioritizes thinking on the present and the future. It highlights a person's assets, such as their knowledge and talents, relationships, satisfying feelings and experiences, and inner drive.

Clinical psychology and positive psychology do not in any way compete with one another. The wellbeing of humans is a priority in both fields. Seligman (1998) asserts that positive psychology is not a more modern invention but has always been a fundamental component of humanist approaches. Unlike to conventional clinical psychology, which primarily focuses on assisting individuals who are already struggling with mental health difficulties and are actively seeking therapy, positive psychology extends to everyone, even those without a formal diagnosis.

A Brief Comparison Between Clinical Psychology and Medical Psychology

It focuses on figuring out the symptoms and obstacles to finding a remedy..

1. *Directs attention to productive ideas, feelings, and behaviors to find solutions.*
2. *It aims to validate hypotheses and combine disparate data to better understand and treat mental disorders. Its primary purpose is to promote happiness and bases its activities on ideas that promote well-being.*
3. *It looks to the past to explore the causes that led to the current situation. It explores both the present and the future to discover more effective ways of living.*
4. *It covers topics such as education, learning disorders, depression, stress, addiction and other traumatic experiences, among other topics. It takes into account areas of excellence, including virtues, skills, abilities, and personal growth.*
5. *It continues to work despite the problem. It functions in the absence or presence of psychopathology.*
6. *It emphasizes both prevention and improvement in its approach.*
6. *It acts as a preventive and preventive measure.*

Research on Medical Psychology and General Happiness

The study of mental health has entered a whole new sector with the advent of positive psychology.

1. Mental health and wellness study findings Slade (2010) asserts that mental health services prioritize a person's happiness and take steps to raise it. This study's main purpose was to investigate how positive psychology therapies may be used by mental health providers to shift

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their focus from treating disease to promoting well-being (Coleman, 1999; Slade, 2010). Slade (2010) argues that the main objective of psychiatric and psychological treatments should be to increase well-being. Slade (2010) said that positive psychology emphasizes the unique experiences, emotions, and actions of its participants by drawing on Seligman's work. It operates on two levels: that of the individual, which is defined by a knowledge of noble traits like love, empathy, forgiveness, and optimism; and that of the group or society (including interventions to promote social relationships, social responsibilities, tolerance, altruism and a sense of values). According to Slade (2010), academics and professionals working in the field of mental health should embrace positive psychology's tenets in order to place greater emphasis on a person's whole growth as opposed to only concentrating on their problems. The state's comprehensive methodology for dealing with mental health From a positive perspective, Slade (2010) developed the full-state model (CSM) of mental health. The CSM is also known as the two-factor model of mental health and the two-continuous model of mental health (Suldo & Shaffer, 2008). These two names have the same meaning (Westerhof & Keyes, 2010). The CSM classifies mental health and mental disease into corresponding categories along a continuum ranging from present to absent and high to low (Keyes, 2005). In the end, a person's mental health is determined by how these two factors combine. According to the CSM, signs of excellent mental health include a high degree of wellbeing and a low level of mental disease (for example, depression, anxiety, stress). This discussion's goal is not to minimize mental disease or its signs and symptoms; rather, it is to spread the notion that mental health and well-being are two distinct concepts that interact to determine our total mental health. Unless a person also exhibits high levels of psychological well-being, even the absence of psychopathology does not automatically imply excellent mental health. The CSM's statement was endorsed on the basis that positive psychology is crucial for personal recovery and well-being. The study of positive psychological concepts, such as happiness, hope, motivation, empathy, and self-esteem, has been found to directly affect a person's overall health and well-being (Schrank & Slade, 2007). It advocates for genuine happiness and describes how to live a happy life in the following four ways: The presence of positive emotions and the desire to take part in activities that boost enjoyment, and a sense of accomplishment are characteristics of a happy living. living a full, active life Personal involvement is the process of focusing on one's own sentiments and personality qualities in order to better understand them and then plan one's life accordingly. A meaningful existence is one in which one pursues the core of what it means to be

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happy and attempts to understand oneself better. A person who leads a successful life finds fulfillment and a true feeling of self as a consequence of putting their thoughts into practice and generating fruit. The connection between positive psychology and health The World Health Organization defines health as a "state of entire physical, mental, and social well-being," rather than just the absence of sickness or infirmity (quoted from Park et al., 2016). Eudaemonia, or the optimal operating condition, has been shown to be crucial for preserving physical health, according to studies and medical specialists from across the globe (Ryff & Singer, 1998). According to research conducted by Cohen and colleagues in 2003, those who reported feeling happy, satisfied, or enthusiastic were less likely to get the common cold than people who said they felt depressed, lonely, or angry. According to this research, good emotions are more conducive to improved health, a stronger immune system, and higher resilience than negative ones. Moreover, Kim et al. (2013) found that those who can clearly define their life's mission had a decreased risk of acquiring cardiovascular disease.

When individuals with a history of cardiac dysfunction received effective therapies, their condition quickly improved and their risk of recurrence was decreased. Interventions for good mental health that improve overall wellbeing The methods to mental health treatment discussed in the following paragraphs may help make the objective of medical psychology—improving people's quality of life—a reality.

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (commonly known as CBT)

Cognitive behavioral therapy, or CBT for short, is one of the most popular forms of psychotherapy utilized today. It is consistent with the ideas of personal wellness and the therapeutic process. The phrase "psychosocial treatment" is often used to describe CBT. Equal responsibility for the client's journey toward rehabilitation rests with both the client and the therapist. Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) encourages constructive thinking, self-motivated behavior, and appropriate room for self-expression, which helps individuals improve their inner resources and resilience (Kuyken et al., 2011). The fundamental tenet of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is the notion that our own beliefs are at the heart of our issues. On the basis of this assumption, CBT aims to alter our thoughts, feelings, and behaviors in order to increase our levels of self-awareness. It has been shown that CBT is effective in treating mental health issues including anxiety, depression, and mood disorders (eg, Chambless & Ollendick, 2001; DeRubeis & Crits-Christoph, 1998). Cognitive

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behavioral therapy (CBT), which is predicated on the notion that people have the capacity to effect the changes they desire in their own life, places a strong emphasis on helping patients develop a self-directed attitude.

Awareness

The "art of being present" or mindfulness practice is a set of helpful abilities that support overall wellbeing and a feeling of inner serenity. Spiritual practices such as mindfulness place an emphasis on letting go of the past and paying attention to the present. Its roots may be found in yogic and Buddhist traditions from long ago. The practice of mindfulness has been demonstrated to be useful in treating a number of mental health issues, mood regulation, lifestyle modification, post-traumatic stress disorder aftercare, and counseling for emotional support (Ackerman, 2017). Positive treatments based on mindfulness have been shown to improve participants' subjective well-being and are advantageous to both clinical and non-clinical groups (Grossman et al., 2004). Niemiec (2013) offered a persuasive justification of the relationship between awareness and the growth of individual strengths, successful outcomes, and admirable character. According to him, conscious positive therapies that foster intrinsic motivation and encourage us include mindfulness-based power practice (MBSP), mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT), mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR), and mindfulness-based meditation techniques. general satisfaction.

Using narrative in therapy The following three elements of narrative psychotherapy are employed to harness the power of self-expression (Smyth, 1998):

“There is no reluctance to communicate or voice what we feel.”

Clients in narrative psychotherapy are encouraged to write about their emotional experiences in order to recognize unhealthy thought patterns and create better ones. In certain forms of narrative psychotherapy, patients are urged to compose a tale based on their own experiences and think about how they may be able to change unfavorable results into more favorable ones. Narrative psychotherapy may help people who struggle to express themselves, are naturally introverted, have high levels of hostility, or have trouble regulating their anger (Christensen & Smith, 1993).

Psychotherapy by Reminiscence

Among the conventional types of therapy that try to enhance patients' wellbeing via activities that concentrate on the present or the future, reminiscence therapy (RT) stands out. Robert Butler, a

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geriatric psychiatrist, was the first to put out the idea that looking back on the past might be beneficial in 1960. Butler (1960) proposed that reflecting on former events, especially when one nears death or suffers a severe depressive episode, enables one to put one's present life in the appropriate perspective. It's not important to reflect on the past. It is all about comprehending the "present" more fully through considering the past. Reminiscence therapy's objective is to boost a person's feeling of contentment and self-worth. Older adults may talk with the therapist about their experiences and share those recollections with them since recalling the past may work as a catalyst for self-expression and emotional catharsis. RT is the ideal therapy for dementia and Alzheimer's disease in addition to being advantageous for the senior population. Patients get educational cues during this therapy to aid with their memory of prior experiences. Reminiscence therapy aims to encourage positive emotions like pleasure and optimism. Participants are invited to share their recollections and to talk about their experiences and ideas. The client's perception of feeling heard and important during the course of therapy is influenced by the therapist's ability to actively listen. When undergoing therapy in an unstructured environment, clients are encouraged to be more truthful and open with one another. Participants get the chance to grow their viewpoints and learn from their peers when RT is provided as group therapy. It encourages pleasant interactions and better social interaction amongst people. 5 Positive Activities To Enhance Your Mental Health Ben-Shahar (2007) asserts that the act of positive practice is equivalent to the quest of genuine pleasure and the growth of limitless satisfaction. His studies on the science of happiness demonstrate that by taking a few simple and practical steps like:

Having a grateful heart and mind A sense of purpose and fulfillment can be brought into our lives (Diener & Diener, 1996).

They are referred to as "happy boosters" and include things like going to work, doing crafts, and spending time with family, among other things. Just about how your life could be without these things and how you might respond if you weren't allowed to interact with them.

Gaining wisdom from one's mistakes and failures

If we allow them, even the most depressing circumstances may teach us important truths about life. According to Ben-2007 Shahar's research, a person's upbringing may make them more resilient to the negative effects of stress. Also, as we conquer obstacles, we have a greater appreciation for the life we already lead.

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Developing an attitude of gratitude

Consistently leading a healthy lifestyle While studies has proven that having a healthy lifestyle helps individuals be happier, it is also true that happiness may enhance our lifestyle. Ben Shahar (2007) found that maintaining a healthy lifestyle acts as the body's built-in healing mechanism. Healthy lifestyle choices include a balanced diet, enough sleep, and regular exercise reduced the chance of physical and mental disease development as well as psychological distress (Trudel-Fitzgerald et al., 2018). Our mood serves as a bridge that connects our thoughts and deeds. We may determine how we are feeling right now by examining our mood. Making a customized mood chart might help us keep track of our mood changes. It may also aid in our comprehension of our emotional state. Making a mood chart is an easy and enjoyable exercise. You should be sincere with yourself and record your emotions and thoughts throughout the day in a journal. Spend a few minutes each day writing in your mood diary and see how it enhances your understanding of who you are. Critical details about the following: Across the whole globe, one in every eight persons experiences mental illness. Mental disease is characterized by significant impairments in thinking, the capacity to control emotions, or behavior. There are several mental disorders from which to pick. Both preventative actions and efficient treatments are available. The overwhelming majority of people lack access to quality medical care. The distinguishing characteristic of a mental disease is a clinically substantial impairment in a person's cognitive, emotional regulation, or behavior.

Argument

Most often, it is accompanied by a restless feeling or a decline in crucial areas of functioning. There are several psychological disorders to choose from. Another word that may be used to describe mental health issues is conditions. This latter term designates a larger group that encompasses mental diseases, psychosocial disorders, and (other) mental ailments linked to excruciating pain, a dysfunctional lifestyle, or a danger of self-harm.

In 2020, when COVID-19 will have spread like an epidemic, there will be a tremendous rise in the number of people who suffer from anxiety and sadness. According to the most recent statistics, anxiety and severe depressive disorders are expected to rise by 26% and 28%, respectively, in only one year. While there are effective preventative and treatment strategies, the great majority of people with mental illness do not have access to them. Many people also experience stigma, discrimination, and infringement of their human rights. Mood Disorders 301 million individuals

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are suffering with anxiety as of 2019, 58 million of them are children and teenagers. Excessive concern and anxiety are hallmarks of anxiety disorders, as are the damaging behaviors linked to these feelings. The symptoms are so severe that they significantly impair a person's capacity to work or cause them to suffer.

There are several different anxiety disorders, including generalized anxiety disorder (characterized by extreme worry), panic disorder (characterized by panic attacks), social anxiety disorder (characterized by extreme fear and worry in social situations), separation anxiety disorder (a deep emotional state of mind) characterized by extreme fear or anxiety about separation from those with whom one has a strong attachment) and others.

In addition to medications, which may be an option depending on the patient's age and the severity of their symptoms, there are psychological therapies that have been shown to be successful.

In 2019, 280 million individuals throughout the globe suffered from depression, including 23 million kids and teenagers. Normal mood swings and the fleeting emotional reactions we often experience to strains and tensions from everyday life are distinct from depression. A depressive episode is defined by the presence of symptoms for at least two weeks, including a depressed mood (feeling empty, irritated, or sad) and a loss of interest or enjoyment in activities. Other symptoms that may be present include difficulty concentrating, strong feelings of guilt or poor self-worth, despair towards the future, thoughts of death or suicide, disrupted sleep, changes in diet or weight, and feeling particularly exhausted or lacking in energy. Depressed people are more likely to succeed in their suicide attempts. Nonetheless, there are psychological approaches that have been successful, and medication may also be a possibility, depending on the patient's age and the severity of their symptoms. Disorder of the mind 40 million individuals were given a bipolar disorder diagnosis in 2019. When someone has bipolar disorder, they sometimes go through manic episodes and then there are periods of depression. The presence of symptoms like a depressed mood (feeling down, agitated, or empty) or a lack of enjoyment or interest in activities for the majority of the day and practically every day for the duration of the episode define a depressive episode. Manic symptoms may also include euphoria or irritation, increased activity or energy, increased talkativeness, racing thoughts, a high sense of self-worth, a reduced need for sleep, distraction, and impulsive unsafe conduct. Those with bipolar disorder have a significant risk of committing suicide. Nonetheless, there are a variety of effective treatment approaches, including

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psychoeducation, stress management, social functioning improvement, and medication therapy. trauma-related stress disorder (PTSD) In communities affected by violence, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and other mental illnesses are prevalent. After enduring a catastrophic incident or sequence of traumatic events, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) may develop. It stands out for each of the following characteristics:

- 1) *re-experiencing the traumatic event or events in the present (included memories, flashbacks, or nightmares);*
- 2) *avoiding thoughts and memories of the event(s), or avoiding activities, situations, or people that remind of the event(s); And*
- 3) *persistent perceptions of the increasing current threat.*

These symptoms considerably impair the person's ability to conduct surgery and have been present for at least a few weeks. There are psychological therapies that work.

Schizophrenia

One in every 300 individuals, or around 24 million people, suffer from schizophrenia worldwide. Schizophrenia patients often live ten to twenty years less than the general population. Significant problems in perceiving the world around them and changes in behavior are characteristics of schizophrenia. Schizophrenia symptoms might include chronic hallucinations or delusions, disordered thinking, wildly disorderly behavior, or extreme agitation. Cognitive difficulties may persist for a very long period in those with schizophrenia. Yet, a variety of effective therapy are accessible, including medication, psychoeducation, family interventions, and psychosocial rehabilitation. In addition to having serious worries about body weight and form, eating disorders like bulimia nervosa and anorexia nervosa are characterized by aberrant eating habits and obsession with food. The person's health is put in grave risk or injury as a consequence of the symptoms or behavior, which results in excruciating agony or a serious impairment of functioning. Anorexia nervosa often develops throughout adolescence or the early stages of adulthood, and the condition has been related to premature mortality from medical conditions or suicide. Bulimia nervosa patients have an extremely high risk of acquiring health issues, indulging in dangerous substance use, and having suicidal thoughts. The effectiveness of a number of therapeutic modalities has been shown, including family-based therapy and cognitive therapy. Disruptive behavior and dissociative disorders A behavior-dyssocial condition, which includes children and

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adolescents, has an impact on the lives of 40 million individuals in 2019. Oppositional defiant disorder is the second asocial condition that comes under the umbrella of disruptive behaviors. One of the two disorders is also referred to as conduct disorder. Persistent behavioral issues, such as persistent resistance or disobedience to conduct that consistently violates others' basic rights or important age-appropriate societal standards, regulations, or laws, are characteristics of disruptive behavior and dissocial disorders. Persistent behavioral issues, such as chronic resistance or disobedience, are what define disruptive conduct and asocial disorders. Yet, this is not always the case. Disruptive and asocial disorders often start in infancy. Effective psychological treatments include cognitive problem-solving and social skill development. Parents, careers, and instructors are often involved in these therapies. neurological conditions Neurodevelopmental disorders are psychiatric diseases that appear during a person's formative years and are marked by severe challenges with learning and carrying out certain mental, physical, linguistic, or social activities. Children, teenagers, and adults may all be impacted by these illnesses. Neurodevelopmental diseases include, but are not limited to, problems like intellectual development disorders, autism spectrum disorders, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). One of the distinguishing characteristics of ADHD is a recurring pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that negatively impacts a person's performance in the classroom, at work, or in social situations. Intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior are severely limited in intellectual development disorders. The challenges with common conceptual, social, and practical abilities used in daily life are referred to as these limits in intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior. The term "autism spectrum disorder" (ASD) refers to a wide range of illnesses marked by some degree of difficulties in social interaction and communication, as well as persistent, constrained, repetitive, and rigid recurring patterns of behavior, interests, or activities. Autism is another name for autism spectrum disorder (ASD). A few of the many effective treatment choices include behavioral treatments, occupational therapy, speech therapy, and psychological therapies. For certain age groups and illnesses, medication is a possible additional therapy option. Who is most likely to be impacted if a mental condition develops? A person's mental health may be either protected from or harmed by a complex network of people, families, communities, and structural components at any one time. While the overwhelming majority of people possess high levels of resilience, those who find themselves in risky conditions like poverty, assault, handicap, or injustice are more vulnerable. A

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person's psychology and biology are specific characteristics of both risk and preventative variables.

Risky variables include genetics, while protective ones include emotional intelligence. Many risk factors and protective variables may be significantly impacted by changes in the structure and/or function of the brain.

Medical Care and Community Assistance Systems

Unfortunately, there is a severe lack of resources and the country's health services are unable to adequately care for persons with mental illness. The demand for therapy is far higher than the supply is everywhere, and when it is available, it is often of worse quality. For instance, just 33% of those who suffer from depression and 29% of those who experience psychosis obtain official mental health therapy. More social support is required for those with mental illness, including help forming and sustaining relationships with friends, family, and the community. Individuals who are mentally ill could also need assistance in order to attend educational programs, get employment or housing, or take part in other activities that are important to them.

WHO reaction The Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan 2013–2030 of the World Health Organization acknowledges the crucial role that mental health plays in the broader objective of promoting health for all people. The strategy has the following four primary goals:

“Improving the effectiveness of mental health leadership and governance; improve access to comprehensive, integrated and responsive mental health and social care services in community-based settings; implementing strategies for the promotion and prevention of mental illness; and improving mental health information systems, evidence and research.”

In order to increase services, particularly in nations with low resources, WHO's Mental Health Gap Action Program (mhGAP) makes use of technical manuals, tools, and training programs that are based on empirical research. It concentrates its capacity-building efforts on non-specialist health care professionals, concentrating on a prioritized set of concerns, as part of an integrated plan to enhance mental health at all levels of treatment. A part of this program is the WHO mhGAP Intervention Guide 2.0, which offers recommendations for the diagnosis and management of mental illness to doctors, nurses, and other healthcare workers working in non-specialty settings. Psychiatry has often focused specifically on diseases connected to mental illness. The field of

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psychiatry constantly discusses mental health, but nobody works to improve it, to paraphrase a remark Mark Twain once made about the weather. After all, mental illness is a condition that can be accurately described, and its limitations are generally clear. Scientific research does not seem to be as applicable to the subject of mental health as value judgements. Mental disease, for instance, may be identified by the presence of certain symptoms, but mental wellness encompasses more than simply the absence of symptoms. Recent versions of the most popular psychiatric textbooks reveal that little practical attention is devoted to good mental health, with the exception of a chapter by Offer and Sabshin in the third and fourth editions of the Comprehensive Textbook of Psychiatry.

Conclusion

Just 5,701 of the 57,800 papers on anxiety and 70,856 on depression found in an electronic search of Psychological Abstracts since 1987 mention life satisfaction, and only 851 of the 851 mention pleasure. The value of one's mental health, however, cannot be overstated. Research on mental health has increasingly moved away from religious preconceptions and toward science during the last 30 years. Ten years ago, when evidence for the reliability of DSM-IV axis V (Global Assessment of Functioning [GAF] Scale) emerged, psychiatry at last had a tool for evaluating mental health (page 32).

In the past, it was widely believed that mental health might be best described as the opposite of mental disease, yet to embrace this idea is to undervalue human potential. Internists started researching the physiology of high altitude around the turn of the 20th century after realizing that health was more than just the absence of symptoms. They also developed effective ways to assess physical health in athletes, pilots, and ultimately astronauts. The condition of being physically healthy is hence the opposite of physical disease. In the late 1930s, Arlie Bock, a Harvard doctor with experience in high altitude physiology and a passion for good physical health, established the Study of Adult Development. It was a cross-disciplinary investigation of good physical and mental health. Bock was concerned about maintaining good physical health. The results of the sixty-year-long study (8) served as the foundation for several parts of this investigation. It is true that figuring out what exactly qualifies as above-average mental health is considerably harder than figuring out what exactly qualifies as physical fitness. Yet it is imperative that the discipline of psychiatry learn from sports medicine and provide precise definitions and standards for what defines good mental

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health. Psychologists have learnt how to assess above-average intellect, just as physiologists have discovered how to assess ordinary intelligence. The area of Psychiatry must follow suit as we do not see an IQ of 100 as the polar opposite of mental retardation. Psychiatrists are often faced with deciding who is mentally fit enough for specific employment since they are asked to determine not only who is too unwell for a work but also who is mentally healthy enough for certain responsibilities. Before a sound definition of mental health can be developed, several measures must be followed. When thinking about mental health, it's important to remember that "average" is not the same as "healthy." This is so because the "average" usually includes a mix of healthy and psychopathological elements. Being in the middle of a regular bell curve may or may not be healthy depending on the circumstances. For instance, the average weight or vision of the general population is in fact unhealthy, and if all factors causing biopsychosocial pathology were taken out of the picture, the population's average IQ would be much higher than 100. The middle dot on the bell curve denotes a normal range for the red blood cell count, body temperature, or mood. The only people with normal eyesight, exercise tolerance, or empathy are those at the top of the bell curve. On the other side, only those who fall below the bell curve have normal levels of bilirubin, narcissism, or serum cholesterol. While discussing mental health, it's important to keep in mind that what constitutes a healthy lifestyle might differ significantly based on a person's location, culture, and age. Being on time is seen as a virtue in certain cultures but as a weakness in others. While General George Patton's competitive temperament was a psychological drawback in times of peace, it proved to be a strength in both of the world wars he served in. Which would you rather have: a type 1 diabetic patient whose blood sugar levels are briefly normal or an Olympic runner who can't race due to a straightforward but temporary ankle fracture? Understanding the dual danger of being "contaminated by values" is the fourth and most crucial cautionary step in defining mental wellness. On the one hand, the study of cultural anthropology makes clear that there are significant cultural differences in how people see mental health. Even if the individual is said to have "excellent" mental health, the issue still exists:

Why? Which is more important: you or society? For the sake of harmony or for the sake of creativity? Which would you choose, happiness or survival?

Who precisely ought to serve as the judge? Erikson remarked, "Healthy personality is an impending issue where the expert transforms into a scared angel" (1, p. 92). On the other hand,

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individuals must use common sense. Anthropology is less significant than biology. The World Health Organization would be foolish to dismiss the universal significance of vitamins and the four basic dietary groups in any discussion of nutrition, despite the fact that diets of various cultures vary. While nearly no activity is seen as deviant across all cultures, this does not always imply that the acceptable behavior is mentally healthy.

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